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Highlights

Improving gamma spectrometry for radionuclide analysis of extraterrestrial samples.

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- Novel methodology developed for low-mass and low-level gamma spectrometry analysis
- Special sample holder designed for a 1-gram pristine extraterrestrial sample
- Re-characterization of HPGe detector efficiency to improve sensitivity at 46.54 keV for ^{210}Pb
- Apparent specific activities of ^{238}U , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{235}U , and ^{40}K measured on a 1.07 g JSC Mars-1 simulant

Improving gamma spectrometry for radionuclide analysis of extraterrestrial samples.

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Abstract

1 With the recent return of extraterrestrial material from the Chang'E 5
2 and Chang'E 6 missions, and the upcoming Mars Sample Return mission,
3 it is essential to develop optimised methodologies for their analysis. These
4 samples are rare and valuable, typically consisting of low-mass, fine-powdered
5 regolith with very low natural radioactivity. This work, carried out at the
6 Laboratoire National Henri Becquerel (LNE-LNHB), presents an adapted
7 gamma-ray spectrometry methodology to determine the activity concentra-
8 tions of natural radionuclides in extraterrestrial samples, with a particular
9 focus on understanding the mobility of ²²²Rn in planetary regoliths and at-
10 mospheres/exospheres.

11 A bespoke sample holder was designed to minimise gamma-ray self atten-
12 uation, particularly in the low energy range, while providing the gas-tightness
13 and inert handling conditions necessary to preserve pristine extraterrestrial
14 material. In addition, a high-purity germanium gamma spectrometer with
15 an active anti-coincidence veto was optimised to increase detection efficiency,
16 with an particular focus on the 46.54 keV emission of ²¹⁰Pb. To validate this
17 methodology, a Martian regolith analog (JSC Mars-1) was analysed immedi-
18 ately after enclosure, with a total measurement time of 36.25 days.

This approach allowed for precise quantification of radionuclides in ex-
traterrestrial samples, overcoming the challenges posed by their low mass,
precious and difficult-to-handle nature. The measured specific activities (ac-
tivity per unit mass of material) with expanded uncertainties (k=2) for ²³⁸U,

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^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{235}U , and ^{40}K were $28.6 \pm 5.7 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$, $19.8 \pm 3.6 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$, $15.4 \pm 2.5 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$, $0.13 \pm 0.03 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$, $146 \pm 12 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$, respectively, compatible with reported data on much larger sample masses. These results demonstrate the capability of this optimised methodology to aid in the radiological characterization of extraterrestrial materials while ensuring minimal sample usage.

Keywords: gamma spectrometry, regolith, radon, extraterrestrial environment, planetary body

19 **1. Introduction**

20 In total, about 386 kg of extraterrestrial material has been returned to
21 Earth. The majority, 99.96%, comes from lunar missions, with much smaller
22 but scientifically invaluable amounts from asteroid, comet, and solar wind
23 missions. These extraterrestrial sample return missions have significantly
24 advanced our understanding of the solar system by bringing back materials
25 from various celestial bodies [1]. The key characteristics of extraterrestrial
26 samples are their rarity and limited availability to the scientific community.
27 Since most of them come from the surface of airless planetary bodies, they
28 originate mainly from impact-induced regoliths and have grain sizes ranging
29 from micrometers to several millimeters [2]. The study of the radionuclides
30 present in these samples provides unique opportunities for radioactive dat-
31 ing and tracking of natural processes with broad applications in geophysics
32 and environmental sciences [3]. Of particular interest is the study of ^{222}Rn .
33 Within the ^{238}U decay chain, ^{222}Rn is known to be one of the major con-
34 tributors to atmospheric radioactivity due to its ability to escape from rock
35 grains and be released into the atmosphere upon decay of its parent radionu-
36 clide, ^{226}Ra [4]. With a half-life of 3.8 days, it is used as a tracer gas to study
37 lithospheric dynamics and atmosphere-lithosphere exchanges [5]. In extrater-
38 restrial environments such as the Moon, ^{222}Rn is considered as an important
39 tracer of lunar outgassing [6, 7]. Its use as a tracer gas can also improve
40 models of volatile transport in the subsurface and exosphere/atmosphere of
41 the Moon and other planets such as Mars and Mercury [8, 9, 10, 11, 12].
42 Therefore, analysis of ^{222}Rn mobility in extraterrestrial regoliths can reveal
43 key regolith properties needed to refine volatile transport models. However,
44 handling extraterrestrial material presents several challenges not only be-
45 cause of its low mass and rarity, but also because of its pristine state after

46 collection and return to Earth. These samples have trace material concentra-
47 tions ranging from 1 to 10000 ppbv and are typically delivered with masses
48 no larger than ~ 1 g. As a result, non-destructive analyses are required to
49 determine their bulk properties, and both storage conditions and analytical
50 setups must ensure minimal exposure of the sample to terrestrial conditions.
51 For this reason, such materials are stored in curation centers that provide
52 inert conditions and should only be moved outside of such centers for short
53 periods of time.

54 A first approach to radon analysis is to determine the content of nat-
55 urally occurring radionuclides, specifically the ^{238}U decay chain, but also,
56 concomitantly, the ^{232}Th decay chain and ^{40}K , which are the most abundant
57 naturally occurring radionuclides in the Earth's crust. For this purpose,
58 gamma-ray spectrometry is the reference method for the measurement of
59 naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM). Due to the limited avail-
60 ability of extraterrestrial material, the typically low concentration of NORM
61 in extraterrestrial regoliths, the needs for non-destructive techniques, and
62 the short period of time a sample should remain outside of curation facilities,
63 the use of low-level gamma spectrometry stands out as the most appropri-
64 ate technique. Among all the available devices for gamma-ray spectrometry,
65 high-purity germanium (HPGe) detectors are the most widely used solution
66 due to their excellent energy resolution, which allows the discrimination of
67 close gamma-ray lines and a better signal-to-noise ratio [13]. To achieve
68 the sensitivity required to detect low concentrations of NORMs, the detec-
69 tor must be shielded from external radiation using both passive and active
70 shielding. To increase counts and reduce acquisition time, the detection effi-
71 ciency, defined as the fraction of gamma rays emitted by the sample that are
72 detected, must be as high as possible over the desired energy range. Several
73 developments have been made to improve detection efficiency [14], including
74 the design of 4π $\alpha\beta$ - γ detectors; and improved shielding systems [15, 14, 16],
75 that implement and optimise modern anti-coincidence veto systems using
76 digital electronics and advanced background characterization techniques.

77 In this paper, we present the improvements made to the low-level gamma
78 spectrometry setup at the Laboratoire National Henri Becquerel (LNHB-
79 LNE), based on an HPGe detector. These modifications were designed to
80 accommodate a 1-gram Chang'E 5 lunar sample and to analyze its NORM
81 content over an acquisition period of one month. With a particular focus on
82 radon gas, the system was optimised to measure the activity of radionuclides
83 from the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th chains, allowing the determination of the ^{222}Rn pro-

84 duction term for further analysis of its emanation coefficient.

85

86 **2. Materials and methods**

87 *2.1. Analog extraterrestrial sample description*

88 Based on the reported concentration of 1.05 ppm of ^{238}U in a lunar sample
89 returned from the Chang'E 5 mission [17, 18], and assuming a sample mass
90 of 1 g, we define a target detection threshold of approximately 12 mBq.

91 Based on this value, we have selected a sample whose reported concen-
92 tration of ^{238}U is similar to that found on Chang'E 5 samples. JSC Mars-1 is
93 a Martian regolith simulant derived from weathered volcanic ash from Pu'u
94 Nene, Hawaii, USA and is designed to mimic the composition and spectral
95 characteristics of bright Martian surface regions [19, 20].

96 Although not a lunar analog, it has already been analysed by gamma
97 spectrometry, and was found to have similar NORM abundances as Chang'E
98 5 and a large range of Apollo samples [21]. These data are valuable for
99 evaluating the design of the experimental setup and the methodology used.
100 In addition, this sample has a high emanation coefficient of $64.4 \pm 6.4\%$ [21],
101 which means that a large fraction of the ^{222}Rn gas is able to escape from the
102 sample grains. This high emanation coefficient is also useful for testing the
103 tightness of the system against radon leakage.

104 *2.2. Requirements and constraints*

105 An extraterrestrial sample is a low-mass, low-radioactivity material that
106 must be transported from the curation facility to a laboratory in a specially
107 designed holder to minimise the risk of contamination. This requirement
108 applies not only to NORMs, but to any form of contamination, particularly
109 by O_2 and H_2O , to preserve the scientific integrity of the sample for long-term
110 study by multiple research communities.

111 The reported value of 12 mBq of ^{238}U serves as a practical sensitivity
112 requirement for our experimental design and evaluation of the minimum de-
113 tectable activity (MDA) performance. Therefore, our experimental setup
114 must be sensitive enough to provide a result with an acceptable level of un-
115 certainty while keeping the acquisition time reasonable. This is critical to
116 ensure that the bulk lunar sample is not stored outside the curation facility
117 for extended periods of time.

118

119 To define a methodology that meets these requirements, it is necessary
 120 to analyze which characteristics of the experimental setup influence the de-
 121 termination of the sample activity and how they do so. The activity of a
 122 radionuclide is derived from the spectral analysis of a gamma peak according
 123 to:

$$A = \frac{C_{NET} - C_{NUL}}{t\varepsilon_p T_\varepsilon I_\gamma} F_{COI} F_{CORR}, \quad (1)$$

124 where C_{NET} are the peak counts after curve fitting and Compton signal
 125 suppression, C_{NUL} are the Background counts on the same Region of Interest
 126 (ROI) and t is the acquisition time. ε_p is the full-energy peak (FEP) detection
 127 efficiency of a reference sample and geometry at the emission energy and T_ε
 128 is the efficiency transfer term between the reference sample and the measured
 129 sample. The other terms are I_γ which is the gamma emission intensity, F_{COI}
 130 and F_{CORR} are the coincidence-summing correction and additional correction
 131 factors, respectively. The expression of the MDA is given by [22, 23, 24]:

$$MDA = \frac{(k_{1-\alpha} + k_{1-\beta}) \sqrt{5B \cdot FWHM}}{t\varepsilon_p T_\varepsilon I_\gamma}, \quad (2)$$

132 where $FWHM$ is full width at half maximum resolution of the detector
 133 at the emission energy, B is the sum of the averaged counts over 10 channels
 134 within the vicinity of the peak and the background counts within the ROI
 135 of the emission, and $(k_{1-\alpha} + k_{1-\beta})$ are the confidence factors for the false
 136 positives (α) and false negatives (β) occurrences.

137 Of all these terms, ε_p and T_ε are the terms that vary most significantly to
 138 the change of the geometric and material properties of our setup. F_{COI} and
 139 F_{CORR} also depend but in a lesser way and the remaining parameters are
 140 defined either by the spectral peak properties used to determine the activity
 141 of the radionuclide or by the intrinsic properties of the germanium crystal.
 142 Therefore, the sample holder design and measurement geometry must be
 143 optimised to maximise the product $\varepsilon_p T_\varepsilon$, thereby reducing the MDA and
 144 improving the sensitivity of the instrument.

145 Within the ^{238}U decay chain, we have paid particular attention to ^{210}Pb ,
 146 the longest-lived radioactive decay product of ^{222}Rn . Studying its unsup-
 147 ported fraction in the sample could provide insight into ^{222}Rn transport across
 148 extraterrestrial surfaces and into radon night-time accumulation within such
 149 a boundary. ^{210}Pb is characterised by a single gamma emission at a low en-
 150 ergy of 46.54 keV, making it a challenging target for detection with sufficient
 151 sensitivity.

152 *2.3. Detector description*

153 To achieve the sensitivity and resolution required to analyse a sample with
154 low mass and low NORM concentration, we used a 66.0 ± 0.5 mm diameter
155 and 220 cm^3 N-type reverse-electrode coaxial high-purity germanium detec-
156 tor (GeHP3). It has a relative efficiency of 51.6% compared to a thallium-
157 activated sodium iodide (NaI(Tl)) in standardised conditions at the 1.3 MeV
158 emission of ^{60}Co and a peak to Compton ratio (P/C) of 62.4. The detector is
159 installed in a laboratory buried under 1.5 m of reinforced concrete and 1 m of
160 soil. There is 50 hPa of overpressure to prevent radon from exhalating from
161 the walls.

162 The detector, with model number GR5021, was manufactured and in-
163 stalled by Canberra Industries Inc. (Mirion Technologies, Belgium) in 2001.
164 It is housed in a measurement chamber that combines passive and active
165 shielding Figure 1. The passive shielding consists of several layers of materials
166 arranged from the outside in: first, 10 cm of low-activity lead ($A < 50 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$)
167 to attenuate external gamma radiation; second, 3 mm of cadmium alloy
168 ($A < 50 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$) to absorb thermal neutrons; third, 5 cm of very low-activity
169 lead ($A < 10 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$) to attenuate gamma radiation emitted by the neutron-
170 activated cadmium; finally, 4 mm of copper shielding to attenuate X-rays
171 originating from the lead shielding.

172 Surrounding this passive shield there is an active shielding consisting of
173 5 cm thick BC-408 plastic scintillators, coupled to five photomultiplier tubes
174 (PMTs) that collect the scintillation light signals Figure 1. These signals
175 are summed and amplified before being analysed by an anti-coincidence veto
176 system with an extendable gate that allows a variable dead time [25].

Figure 1: Schematic cross section of the GeHP3 detector and its shielding (not to scale). The anti-cosmic veto consists of 5 plastic scintillators and 5 PMTs surrounding the passive shielding. The passive shielding is a combination of different layers: low activity lead (10 cm thickness on each side, expected bottom part: 15 cm), cadmium (4 mm), 5 cm of ultra-low activity lead and 6 mm of copper.

177 The measurement chamber is continuously purged with nitrogen gas from
 178 the detector's liquid nitrogen Dewar at a flow rate of 30 L h^{-1} . This purging
 179 effectively removes radon gas from the cavity, reducing its concentration from
 180 an average volume activity of 20 Bq m^{-3} in the room to undetectable levels,
 181 approximately one hour after closure. The room temperature is fixed at
 182 $20 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

183 Although some studies of environmental radioactivity conducted under
 184 mountains may achieve lower background levels [26, 27], the current setup
 185 and its shielding are optimal for this application, since the goal is to analyze

186 natural radionuclides in natural samples, specially radon decay products,
187 which can reach high levels in underground facilities. Although effective
188 radon mitigation strategies are available for such environments, the natural
189 radon concentration in underground laboratories is generally higher than in
190 surface labs. In our case, the combination of an efficient anti-radon system,
191 low ambient background, and on-site accessibility renders the current config-
192 uration technically and operationally adequate for the number and frequency
193 of measurements we intend to perform using this methodology. Moreover, at
194 this level of isolation, the main source of contribution in the analysis arises
195 not from the environment, but from the sample itself. For example, if we
196 aim to study the ^{210}Pb emission located in the low-energy range ($<100\text{ keV}$),
197 the signal will be located within the Compton continuum. It will also be
198 overlapped by X-ray fluorescence from the radionuclides in the sample, the
199 detector materials, and the sample holder. This occurs regardless of how
200 well the measurement system is isolated from external radiation. Although
201 a Compton suppressor system could be added, it is not feasible for us due to
202 budgetary and operational constraints.

203 Careful determination of the background signal is a critical step in mea-
204 suring the activity of naturally occurring radionuclides. Therefore, it is es-
205 sential to perform a thorough analysis of the instrument background signal
206 and its variations over long measurements.

207 The detector window is made of a carbon-epoxy composite, chosen for its
208 low atomic number NORM content, which minimises gamma and X-ray at-
209 tenuation while maximising detection efficiency and keeping residual natural
210 radionuclides concentrations low. The end-cap and crystal holder are both
211 made of low background aluminium. The preamplifier is located outside the
212 detector housing.

213 In addition, the system originally included a 1.12 mm thick copper screen
214 right on top of the detector window to shield the detector from X-rays origi-
215 nating from the samples. However, one of the goals of this study was to im-
216 prove the sensitivity of the detection system to the 46.54 keV ^{210}Pb gamma
217 emission, which was strongly attenuated by this screen. Therefore, the copper
218 layer was removed to increase the detection efficiency in this energy range.

219 This modification introduced a significant variation in the detector's ef-
220 ficiency, making it necessary to reconstruct the efficiency curves of the in-
221 strument and re-characterise its overall performance. For this purpose, we
222 used ETNA (Efficiency Transfer for Nuclide Activity measurements)[28], a
223 software developed at LNHB, to calculate efficiency transfer coefficients and

224 coincidence summation corrections based on the newly obtained experimen-
225 tal efficiencies.

226 *2.4. Sample holder design*

227 The design of an optimised sample holder for gamma spectrometry must
228 ensure that the sample geometry minimises gamma-ray self-attenuation and
229 that the construction material neither absorbs nor adsorbs gases while al-
230 lowing gamma-ray transmission. The holder must be hermetic, both under
231 vacuum and at a given pressure, and its internal volume should be minimised
232 to prevent secondary radionuclide deposition due to radon gas escape from
233 the sample, that could alter the measurement geometry. Finally, the design
234 should favor off-the-shelf components to reduce costs and ensure availability.

235 The optimal sample geometry was determined for a cylindrical volume
236 corresponding to 1 g of the JSC Mars-1 sample. The primary optimization
237 factor was the detection efficiency in the low-energy range, which is critical for
238 the analysis of certain radionuclides such as ^{210}Pb . Using the ETNA software,
239 multiple efficiency transfer simulations were performed for a cylinder with
240 varying diameters while keeping the total volume constant. The efficiency
241 transfer values were then analysed for different energy values and cylinder
242 radii, identifying the optimal radius for each energy. A weighted average was
243 applied to these values, assigning higher weights to geometries that improved
244 low-energy efficiency.

245 To ensure air tightness and material compatibility of the sample holder,
246 a 316L stainless steel CF40 flange was selected while the seal is made with
247 a copper gasket. The interaction between these materials provides a high-
248 vacuum seal and prevents any material from entering or leaving the flange.
249 This aspect is particularly critical for ^{222}Rn , which could potentially escape
250 from the holder and create a secular disequilibrium between the parents
251 (^{238}U , ^{234}Th , ^{226}Ra) and the decay products (^{214}Pb , ^{214}Bi). To evaluate this
252 possibility, we compared the measured activities of ^{226}Ra , ^{214}Pb , and ^{214}Bi . If
253 there were disequilibrium, the activities would not match, indicating a ^{222}Rn
254 deficit inside the sample holder cavity.

255 *2.5. Background characterisation*

256 One of the particular challenges in the analysis of environmental radia-
257 tion, and radon in particular, is that the NORMs of interest present in the
258 sample, which belong to the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay chains, are also present in
259 the detector surroundings and correspond to the major source of interference.

260 For this reason, a thorough characterization of the background is essential to
261 properly distinguish it from the signal emitted by the sample.

262 Initially, ten background acquisitions were performed using the experi-
263 mental setup without a sample holder, resulting in a total acquisition time
264 of 51.11 days. Later, to evaluate the potential contribution of the sample
265 container itself, two additional acquisitions were carried out using the same
266 detector: one with the CF40 sample holder used for this study, and one
267 with a pristine, unused holder. Each measurement lasted approximately 14.4
268 and 6.7 days, respectively. This comparison aimed to assess whether radon
269 daughter deposition during previous sample measurements contributed to the
270 observed signal.

271 2.6. Auto-attenuation

272 As mentioned in subsection 2.2, ε_p and T_ε depend not only on the mea-
273 surement geometry but also on the sample materials and thus, to estimate
274 the detection efficiency, it is important to evaluate how much the sample at-
275 tenuates the gamma rays it emits. For this purpose, we used an experimental
276 setup at LNHB consisting of a HPGe detector, two collimators with a beam
277 diameter of 8 mm, a sample holder and a support for an external radioactive
278 source Figure 2. This geometry ensures that the gamma rays intersect the
279 sample surface at angles sufficiently close to 90° , making the application of
280 Equation 3 a valid approximation.

281 Self-attenuation analysis is a relative measurement using an external ra-
282 dioactive source, such as ^{152}Eu and ^{133}Ba , chosen for its wide range of emis-
283 sion peaks over different energies, extending down to 40.12 keV. Two acqui-
284 sitions are performed: one with an empty sample holder and one with the
285 holder containing the material. By analyzing how the intensities of multiple
286 ^{152}Eu and ^{133}Ba emission peaks are reduced, the linear attenuation coefficient
287 (μ) is determined from the ratio of their peak areas, as defined by:

$$\mu(E) (\text{cm}^{-1}) = \frac{-\ln\left(\frac{N(E)}{N_0(E)}\right)}{h}, \quad (3)$$

288 where h is the thickness of the sample in cm, $N(E)$ is the count rate of
289 a specific emission at energy E (corrected for source decay) with the sample
290 and $N_0(E)$ is the count rate without the sample.

291 Finally, the linear attenuation coefficient $\mu(E)$ was obtained by fitting the
292 experimental data to a power law model of the form $\mu(E) = a \cdot E^b$ using

293 weighted non-linear least squares regression. The weights applied in the fit
 294 correspond to the absolute uncertainty of each measured μ value. The result-
 295 ing fit parameters were then used to evaluate μ at specific photon energies
 296 relevant to the gamma emissions of interest. This set of data was used as
 297 input to the ETNA software to calculate the efficiency transfer term T_ϵ from
 298 the reference geometry to our measurement geometry.

Figure 2: Set-up of the auto-attenuation experiment done at LNHB, the free space for the sample is adjusted depending on the sample thickness.

299 2.7. Efficiency curves

300 After removing the 1.12mm thick circular copper screen (see subsection
 301 2.3), the detection efficiency increased and could be modeled using
 302 ETNA. However, the resulting efficiency transfer values T_ϵ were high, for
 303 example, at the emission energy of 46.54 keV for ^{210}Pb , the coefficient was
 304 145.44, too large to be used in the activity calculations due to its uncer-
 305 tainty. To address this, new efficiency calibration curves were determined

306 experimentally using a set of standard radioactive sources with known activ-
 307 ities. Two standard geometry configurations were used: configuration 1 was
 308 a point source placed 10 cm from the detector, and configuration 2 was a
 309 standardised SG50 geometry. This geometry consists of a container made of
 310 polyethylene (C_2H_4) with an inner diameter of 36.6 mm filled with a 50 mL
 311 solution of radionuclides in 0.1 M HCl reaching 47.52 mm in height. This
 312 container was placed in direct contact with the detector.

313 In order to fully characterise the instrument after the removal of the
 314 copper screen, total and FEP efficiency curves were generated:

315 *2.7.1. Total efficiency curve*

316 The total efficiency ε of a detector for a given energy E is defined as the ra-
 317 tio between the number of interactions (FEP or Compton scattering) caused
 318 by photons of energy E and the total number of photons of the same energy
 319 emitted by the source [29]. It corresponds to the probability of interaction
 320 between a gamma ray of energy E emitted by a source and the detector. This
 321 curve thus characterises the total response of the detector and is needed to
 322 calculate the coincidence-summation correction factor F_{COI} , which is used
 323 for further calculations.

324 The total efficiency of the instrument was determined using configuration
 325 1. The set of radioactive sources was chosen to be mono-energetic and is
 326 detailed in the inset of Figure 6.

327 The total efficiency value was obtained by integrating the FEP emission
 328 and its Compton contribution, capturing all gamma-ray interactions within
 329 the germanium crystal. When necessary, X-ray emissions from the source
 330 were removed to eliminate unwanted contributions not related to gamma-ray
 331 emissions. This was done by manually modifying the channel counts within
 332 the ROI of the X-ray peaks, replacing their values with estimates interpolated
 333 from the surrounding Compton continuum.

334 After obtaining the experimental values, we used the ACORES fitting al-
 335 gorithm [30], developed at LNHB, to perform a polynomial fit of the efficiency
 336 ε as defined by:

$$\ln(\varepsilon) = \sum_{k=1}^P a_k \cdot (\ln(E))^{k-1}, \quad (4)$$

337 where a_k is the set of fitting coefficients. This procedure was applied
 338 consistently to all efficiency curves.

339 *2.7.2. Full-energy peak efficiency curve*

340 The peak efficiency ε_p of a detector for a given gamma-ray energy E is
341 defined as the ratio of the number of photons that deposit their full energy
342 in the detector, i.e. those contributing to the FEP, to the total number of
343 photons of energy E emitted by the source. Unlike total efficiency, which
344 includes all detectable interactions, peak efficiency accounts only where the
345 entirety of the gamma ray energy is deposited in the active volume of the
346 germanium crystal.

347 To obtain this curve, radioactive sources with multiple emissions over
348 different energy ranges and stable decay products were selected to avoid
349 interferences.

350 This efficiency value corresponds to ε_p in Equation 1 and 2, and serves
351 as a reference for applying efficiency transfer corrections to the measurement
352 geometry. To obtain the FEP efficiency curve, we used configuration 2.

353 *2.8. Gamma-ray spectrum analysis*

354 The gamma spectrum analysis was performed using InterWinner 7 (ITECH
355 Instruments, France) [31]. For each full-energy peak (FEP), the region of in-
356 terest (ROI) was defined, the Compton continuum subtracted, and the net
357 peak area extracted by fitting the peak to a Gaussian function. This approach
358 is suited to our counting statistics and enables consistent treatment of closely
359 spaced or low-intensity peaks. The software also performs background sig-
360 nal reduction and associates each peak with a radionuclide using the LARA
361 database [32], based on a user-defined table of isotopes and emissions.

362 After obtaining the net counts with Compton signal and background sub-
363 traction, the remaining terms from Equation 1 were applied to determine the
364 activity of the emitting radionuclide.

365 As part of the additional corrections, a theoretical correction factor F_{CORR}
366 of 0.58 was applied to the ^{226}Ra gamma emission to account for interference
367 with the ^{235}U emission peak. This correction assumes that both radionuclides
368 are in secular equilibrium within their respective decay chains and that the
369 sample contains natural uranium, i.e., with a $^{235}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ activity ratio consis-
370 tent with unprocessed material [33].

371 When multiple emissions of the same radionuclide are analysed, a weighted
372 average was calculated, giving greater weight to results with lower uncer-
373 tainty. The uncertainty budget for the major emissions of the natural ra-
374 dionuclides detected in JSC Mars-1 is shown in Table 1.

Components	Relative standard uncertainties (%)				
	²³⁸ U (²³⁴ Th) (93.3 keV)	²²⁶ Ra	²¹⁴ Pb (351.93 keV)	²¹⁴ Bi (609.31 keV)	²¹⁰ Pb
FEP efficiency ε_p determination (configuration 1)	2.08	1.86	1.74	1.73	2.02
Efficiency transfer T_ε (configuration 2)	3.8	1.4	1.0	0.8	15.33
Coincidence summing correction factor	0.21	0	0.03	2.49	0
External correction factors (²³⁵ U effects)	0	4.24	0	0	0
Net counts peak areas, Compton and background subtraction	9.24	7.3	3.87	4.87	13.8
Gamma ray probability	2.13	0.53	0.2	0.42	0.94
Sample quantity (weight)	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93
Sample linear attenuation coefficient (μ)	12.51	13.43	14.31	15.10	11.69
Combined standard uncertainty	10.3	8.8	4.6	8.5	20.8

Table 1: Standard uncertainty budget of the main emissions of the ²³⁸U natural decay chain radionuclides found in JSC-Mars 1.

375 2.9. Minimum detectable activity (MDA)

376 To calculate the MDA, we used $k_{1-\alpha} = k_{1-\beta} = 1.645$, corresponding to
377 a 5% level of false positive and false negative events. The resulting MDA
378 expression is given by:

$$MDA = \frac{7.36\sqrt{B \cdot FWHM}}{t\varepsilon_p T_\varepsilon I_\gamma}, \quad (5)$$

379 where the value B is the averaged counts over 10 channels in the vicinity
380 of the peak signal. However, since the NORMs we are interested in are also
381 present in the background spectrum, we also took the area of the emission
382 peak present in the background within the same ROI and added it to the
383 averaged counts.

384 Compton scattering of gamma rays from the sample contributes to the
385 surrounding continuum near the peak of interest. Therefore, to obtain rep-
386 resentative MDA results, we used a sample with a radionuclide composition
387 similar to that of the sample under study so we could make an a priori assess-
388 ment of the sensitivity of the setup. This approach allows for a more realistic
389 assessment of the setup's sensitivity to lunar regolith samples by approxi-
390 mating the expected Compton background from their natural radionuclide
391 composition.

392 In this case, the JSC Mars-1 NORM concentration is comparable to that
393 of a lunar sample returned by the Chinese Chang'E 5 mission [21, 18] and is
394 therefore suitable for MDA analysis.

395 **3. Results and discussion**

396 *3.1. Sample holder geometry and design*

397 The optimal radius values for each energy correspond to a constant vol-
398 ume of 1.25 cm^3 of JSC Mars-1, equivalent to 1 g of material (Figure 3). The
399 results indicate that the optimal radius for our measurement system falls
400 within a narrow range of less than 1.2 mm (from 15.7 to 17 mm).

401 The resulting weighted average gives a radius of 16.18 mm and a thickness
402 of 1.52 mm. For manufacturing and assembly reasons, the final geometry was
403 fixed to a cylinder with a radius of 16 mm and a thickness of 1.5 mm. The
404 selected sample holder design consists of a 16 mm radius cavity machined
405 into the bottom of a CF flange to hold the sample (Figure 4). At the top, a
406 welded piston fits tightly into the cavity, leaving no gaps at the side edges.
407 The depths are set so that the free space between the top and bottom parts
408 is 1.5 mm, ensuring minimal empty space inside the holder.

409 The bottom thickness of the flange was set to $500 \mu\text{m}$ to minimise gamma-
410 ray attenuation by the sample holder while remaining at the feasible limit
411 of structural integrity and manufacturability. The attained thickness was
412 $876 \pm 41 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 3: Optimal radius obtained for each energy within the defined detector constraints. The red dashed line corresponds to the average weighted value. Three main emission of the radionuclides ^{210}Pb , ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi are marked in red.

Figure 4: Final dimensions and design of the CF sample holder.

413 *3.2. Auto-attenuation results for JSC Mars*

414 For the self-attenuation measurement, two acquisitions were made: one
 415 for 4.62 days with the sample in place, and another for 5.5 days without the
 416 sample Figure 5.

Figure 5: Linear attenuation results for the JSC Mars-1 sample and the power-law fit applied to them.

417 3.3. Efficiency curves

418 The efficiency values obtained in configuration 1 (Figure 6) and configura-
419 tion 2 (Figure 7) show a significant increase in the total and FEP efficiencies
420 of the measurement system and a shift of the maximum efficiency value to-
421 wards lower energies. This indicates that the system has become significantly
422 more effective at detecting low-energy gamma rays after the removal of the
423 copper screen.

424 More specifically, for the ^{210}Pb 46.54 keV emission, the efficiency in con-
425 figuration 2 increased by a factor of 38.3. A summary of the efficiency gains
426 over the calibration curves obtained using configurations 1 and 2, is given in
427 Table 2.

Figure 6: Comparison of the total efficiency curves of the GeHP3 detector before and after removal of the copper screen (configuration 1). Each point corresponds to a measurement made on a point source located 10 cm above the detector with an expanded uncertainty ($k=2$). Three main emission energy levels of the radionuclides ^{210}Pb , ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi are marked in red.

Figure 7: Comparison of the full-energy peak (FEP) efficiency curves of the SG50 geometry in contact with the detector before and after removal of the copper screen (configuration 2). Three main emission energy levels of the radionuclides ^{210}Pb , ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi are marked in red.

Geometry	Setup	Efficiency (%)		
		46.54 keV (^{210}Pb)	92.59 keV (^{234}Th)	609.31 keV (^{214}Bi)
Punctual source @ 10 cm total efficiency (configuration 1)	With Cu	0.23	1.5	1.8
	Without Cu	2.2	2.5	1.9
SG 50 in contact FEP efficiency (configuration 2)	With Cu	0.22	4.8	2.2
	Without Cu	8.7	9.3	2.5

Table 2: Comparison of efficiencies of the different configurations with and without copper screen for three energy levels. These values correspond to the main emission energies of three radionuclides belonging to the ^{238}U decay chain. Each shows the efficiency gain in the low, medium and high energy ranges.

428 3.4. Background characterisation

429 To better assess the influence of the sample's intrinsic signal compared to
 430 the laboratory background, we calculated the ratio between the total counts

431 measured with the sample to the background-only counts in the same FEP.
432 Overall, the sample spectrum exceeds the background by approximately 39%.
433 The observed ratios at given energies are: 1.10 at 46.54 keV (^{210}Pb), 1.43 at
434 63.3 keV (^{234}Th), 1.55 at 92.59 keV (^{234}Th), 1.68 at 186.21 keV (^{226}Ra), 1.25
435 at 351.93 keV (^{214}Pb), and 1.20 at 609.31 keV (^{214}Bi).

436 However, additional background measurements revealed that the sample
437 holder itself may substantially contribute to the observed signal. Acquisitions
438 using both a used and pristine CF40 sample holder showed that several emis-
439 sion peaks exhibit comparable or even higher intensities than those measured
440 with the holder loaded with the JSC Mars-1 sample. This suggests that a
441 significant portion of the detected signal may originate from the holder rather
442 than the sample. Using a pristine flange further rules out radon deposition as
443 the source of this effect. Consequently, the current measurement setup can-
444 not distinguish clearly between the sample signal and the container signal,
445 specially at low energies.

446 3.5. Gamma-ray analysis

447 The measured activity values for the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay chains are
448 shown in Table 3 and Figure 9. These results correspond to a total acquisition
449 time of 36.25 days. The activity values and derived concentrations presented
450 here are based on spectra that have not been corrected for the radiological
451 contribution of the sample holder.

452 Assuming secular equilibrium between ^{238}U and ^{226}Ra , and between ^{232}Th
453 and ^{228}Ac , we obtain ^{238}U and ^{232}Th concentrations of 1.59 ± 0.30 ppm and
454 3.78 ± 0.70 ppm, respectively. These values compare well with a previous
455 study [21] that reported values of 1.05 ± 0.10 ppm (LMRE) and $1.36 \pm$
456 0.30 ppm (LESTS) for ^{238}U , and 3.44 ± 1.00 ppm (LMRE) and 3.29 ± 0.40 ppm
457 (LESTS) for ^{232}Th .

458 Additional discrepancies arise when comparing activity values obtained
459 from different radionuclides within the same decay chain. For instance, us-
460 ing the activity of ^{234}Th , the direct decay product of ^{238}U , we obtain a
461 concentration of 2.3 ± 0.3 ppm, incompatible with the reported values. This
462 discrepancy, clearly shown in Figure 9a, appears between the radionuclides
463 ^{226}Ra , ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi , which are in equilibrium, and ^{234}Th , and ^{210}Pb , all
464 at low energies, which show incompatible activity levels.

465 The case of ^{210}Pb is particularly significant, as it shows the largest dis-
466 crepancy. Although the enhanced detection efficiency in the low-energy range
467 was expected to improve precision, the overestimation remains. While this

468 may be partly due to unsupported ^{210}Pb from ^{222}Rn outgassing, we consider
469 this effect insufficient to fully explain the difference.

470 Several emissions attributed to natural radionuclides present in the stain-
471 less steel flange overlap with key lines such as those from ^{234}Th (63.3 and
472 92.6 keV) and ^{210}Pb (46.54 keV), well within the low-energy region where
473 overestimation is observed. Background measurements performed with empty
474 and pristine sample holders revealed a non-negligible signal contribution in
475 this energy range. While preliminary, this background may explain the over-
476 estimation of these two isotopes, as well as the slight shift observed in the
477 ^{232}Th chain activity values. Due to limited counting statistics, the holder's
478 contribution could not be fully subtracted from the loaded spectra, but it
479 is likely a significant factor in the discrepancies observed at low energy. A
480 more detailed background characterisation of the holder is proposed to im-
481 prove activity attribution in future measurements.

482 In addition to structural background, the spectrum below 100 keV also
483 includes a strong Compton continuum and X-ray fluorescence from elements
484 present in the shielding and sample matrix. These features complicate the
485 identification of weak peaks and can lead to count overestimation when defin-
486 ing the ROI, particularly for low-intensity gamma lines. As shown in Fig-
487 ure 8, peak ROI selections in this range are heavily affected by the surround-
488 ing spectral structure, increasing the risk of residual contamination from the
489 continuum.

Figure 8: Raw spectra of JSC Mars-1 for the region below 100 keV, the red areas correspond to the ROIs used to obtain the net counts of the labelled radionuclide.

490 The detection efficiency itself may also differ from experimental values.
 491 For example, in our geometry, the experimental efficiency for the ^{210}Pb emis-
 492 sion differs by 6.5% from the efficiency curve shown in Figure 7. However,
 493 this deviation alone does not explain the observed overestimation.

494 The efficiency transfer is particularly sensitive in the low-energy range,
 495 where gamma-ray attenuation becomes more pronounced due to changes in
 496 geometry and material composition. In our setup, the primary limiting fac-
 497 tor is not the sample itself, but rather the sample holder, which is made
 498 of INOX 316L. The stainless steel base of the CF40 flange, despite being
 499 thinned to a nominal thickness of 500 μm , introduces significant attenuation
 500 in the low-energy regime, much greater than that of the JSC Mars-1 material.
 501 This structural constraint contributes substantially to the uncertainty of the
 502 efficiency transfer, specially when using a reference configuration, such as the
 503 SG50 geometry, whose container is made of plastic. Additionally, while the
 504 beam diameter used in the self-attenuation experiment (8 mm) provides a suf-
 505 ficiently large footprint to mitigate the effects of inhomogeneous distribution,

506 the measurement remains sensitive to local variations in activity. Spatial in-
507 homogeneities, including grain-to-grain variability and imperfect mixing, can
508 also affect the apparent attenuation at low energies and may contribute to
509 discrepancies between small-volume measurements and bulk configurations.
510 To address these limitations, future improvements could involve replacing
511 the current stainless steel base with a lighter, less attenuating material, such
512 as aluminium. This change would significantly reduce low-energy gamma
513 attenuation and improve overall detection sensitivity.

514 To mitigate these effects, we propose replacing the stainless steel base of
515 the current sample holder with a lighter and less attenuating material, such
516 as low-activity aluminium. Future holders will undergo a detailed analysis
517 of their natural radionuclide content to ensure their contribution can be reli-
518 ably characterised and subtracted from the sample signal. Overtime, sample
519 holders, including those made of aluminum, can accumulate ^{222}Rn daughter
520 products on their surfaces. However, electropolishing prior to use can remove
521 these deposits, and storing them under a controlled nitrogen atmosphere can
522 help prevent further accumulation and/or deposition [34]. In addition, the
523 use of an uranium- and thorium-rich sample as a reference could help to
524 quantify the uncertainties in low-activity measurements more precisely, as it
525 would isolate the effect of the sample material on the efficiency transfer be-
526 tween geometries. These improvements are essential to ensure the reliability
527 of future analyses involving low-mass samples and measurements near the
528 detection limit.

529 Due to the uncorrected contribution of the sample holder, no definitive
530 uncertainty assessment can be made on the measured activities of the JSC
531 Mars-1 sample. As a result, the concentrations presented here should be
532 interpreted as apparent values, subject to background interference in the
533 low-energy region. For the ^{232}Th decay chain, the relative consistency be-
534 tween radionuclide activities suggests a possible secular equilibrium, except
535 for ^{208}Tl , which shows a deficit likely linked to its 35.9% branching ratio.

536 While the activity values of ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi appear compatible with that
537 of ^{226}Ra , the potential contribution of the sample holder prevents a firm
538 conclusion regarding the radon-tightness of the configuration in this mea-
539 surement.

Radionuclide	Activity (Bq kg^{-1})		
	LNHB (this study)	LMRE [21]	LESTS [21]
^{238}U (^{234}Th) (Bq kg^{-1})	28.6 ± 5.7	13.0 ± 1.7	16.8 ± 3.2
^{226}Ra	19.8 ± 3.6	14.6 ± 2.7	14.1 ± 9.6
^{214}Pb	14.1 ± 5.3	6.4 ± 0.8	
^{214}Bi	15.6 ± 6.6	6.7 ± 0.8	
^{210}Pb	43 ± 18	9.3 ± 1.6	
^{232}Th (^{228}Ac)	15.4 ± 2.5	14.0 ± 4.0	13.4 ± 1.6
^{224}Ra	14.8 ± 2.7	13.5 ± 2.3	
^{212}Pb	12.8 ± 1.3	12.8 ± 1.1	
^{212}Bi	15.2 ± 2.4	15.0 ± 4.0	
^{208}Tl	11.6 ± 1.6	4.4 ± 0.5	
^{40}K	146 ± 12		
^{235}U	0.13 ± 0.03		

Table 3: Specific activity (activity per unit mass of material) with expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) obtained for both natural decay chains on 1.07 g of JSC Mars-1 sample (LNHB) and 472 g of the same material (LMRE, LESTS) [21]. The discrepancy for the ^{234}Th and ^{210}Pb is discussed in subsection 3.5.

Figure 9: Specific activity (activity per unit mass of material) with expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) of the radionuclides from the ^{238}U (a) and ^{232}Th (b) decay chains obtained in this study on JSC Mars-1 sample (in blue). The obtained values are compared with those reported at LMRE (in orange) and LESTS (in green) facilities [21]. They are shown by order of appearance in the decay chains. The discrepancy for the ^{234}Th and ^{210}Pb is discussed in subsection 3.5.

540 *3.6. Minimum detectable activity (MDA)*

541 The MDA values presented in Table 4 were calculated without taking into
 542 account the background contribution from the sample holder. Under these
 543 conditions, the sensitivity requirement of 12 mBq for ^{238}U appears to be met
 544 for most emissions, with the exception of the low-energy lines from ^{234}Th at
 545 63.3 keV and ^{210}Pb . These low-energy values are also more susceptible to
 546 overlapping peaks and background complexity, which can affect the accuracy
 547 of the MDA determination.

548 A more detailed characterisation of the sample holder background would
 549 allow for refined MDA estimates in future studies. The use of a low-activity
 550 aluminium holder, as previously proposed, would also improve the reliabil-
 551 ity of MDA estimates by enabling a more accurate characterisation of the
 552 background and at the same time reducing the attenuation of gamma-rays.

Radionuclide	Emission energy (keV)	MDA (mBq)
^{234}Th	63.3	13
^{234}Th	92.59	4.7
^{226}Ra	186.21	5.5
^{214}Pb	351.93	0.71
^{214}Bi	609.31	0.79
^{210}Pb	46.54	39
^{228}Ac	911.2	1.3
^{224}Ra	240.99	4.6
^{212}Pb	238.63	0.40
^{212}Bi	727.33	4.4
^{208}Tl	583.19	0.94
^{40}K	1460.82	4.6
^{235}U	185.72	0.34

Table 4: Preliminary MDA values for each of the main emissions of the ^{238}U decay chain radionuclides for an acquisition of 36.25 days performed on 1.07 g of JSC Mars-1 sample. These values do not take into account the sample holder’s contribution to the background.

553 4. Conclusions

554 This study demonstrates that the gamma spectrometric analysis of nat-
555 ural radionuclides in extraterrestrial samples with very low mass and low
556 NORM content is feasible using a dedicated low-level detection approach.
557 A customised methodology was developed to meet the specific constraints
558 of gram-scale regolith samples, combining an adapted sample holder design,
559 optimised measurement geometry, and improved detector efficiency at low
560 energies. The re-characterisation of the GeHP3 detector and the generation
561 of new efficiency curves successfully enhanced sensitivity in the 30 keV to
562 100 keV range, enabling the detection of key emissions such as those from
563 ^{234}Th and ^{210}Pb .

564 This study also highlights the importance of careful background assess-
565 ment when analysing low-mass samples, particularly in the low-energy range.
566 Based on our results, we identify the contribution of the sample holder as a
567 potential source of spectral distortion and apparent activity overestimation
568 for some radionuclides. Although the measurements presented here are pre-
569 liminary, they underline the value of dedicated holder background character-
570 isation and radiopure material selection. The complexity of the low-energy
571 region, particularly due to the yet uncorrected contribution of the sample
572 holder, prevents us from quantitatively isolating the impact of shielding and
573 the active veto on detection limits in the current study. However, the re-
574 duction in the background level—bringing the count rate close to that of the
575 low-mass sample and its Compton component demonstrates the effectiveness
576 of the passive shielding in enabling such low-activity measurements. More
577 broadly, the identification of the container as a possible contributor to sig-
578 nal bias represents a relevant consideration for other low-level spectrometry
579 applications.

580 This methodology now allows gram-scale measurements of regolith sam-
581 ples, opening the possibility of analyzing statistical dispersion within a larger
582 sample population. This is an important step in assessing the heterogeneity
583 of returned lunar samples from different collection sites and comparing local
584 measurements with orbital data. It provides a framework for characteriz-
585 ing other planetary analogs and supports future studies aimed at extracting
586 geochemical and volatile transport information from rare and fragile extrater-
587 restrial materials.

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